

Phylogenetic biogeography inference using dynamic paleogeography models and explicit geographic ranges

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Supplementary figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Building a pixelation using an equal area partition. *Pix* is the number of pixels at the equator, in this case 12. The expected size of a pixel side is $s_z = 2\pi \times \text{pix} \div 360$. First (left), cut the sphere into $\text{pix} \div 2 + 1$ rings. The rings will all have the same size in latitude (s_z), except for the polar rings, which have half the size ($s_z \div 2$). Second (right), in each ring, the number of pixels is given by the size of the circumference of the ring ($2\pi \times \cos(\text{lat})$); in odd rings, the starting location is shifted by $s_z \div 2$, and pixels are numbered from west to east.

Supplementary Figure 2. Plot of the number of pixels at a given distance (in radians) from 20 random pixels in each ring of an e360 pixelation used in this paper; the pixelation has 180 rings (for a total of 3600 sampled pixels). In red is the number of pixels at a given distance from the North Pole, which is used for quick approximations of the spherical normal in the likelihood calculations.

Supplementary Figure 3. *Effects of the landscape. Two simulations with $\lambda=350$ of 100,000 particles in a branch of 50 Myr, starting at two points at the same latitude but different longitude. Without landscape (top two rows), the distribution of the particle destinations is the same, shifted to their respective longitudes. The second row shows that using time stages (10, i.e., one each 5 Myr) does not change the distribution. In the third row, the landing probability is modified by the landscape (prior of land = 1, prior of water = 0). As a single time stage is used, the distribution is approximately the distribution without the landscape, masked by the landscape. In the bottom row, 10 time stages (each 5 Myr) are used (as is done in the paleogeographic models described in this paper); in this case, few particles were able to cross oceanic barriers (such as the Atlantic when starting from Posadas or the Antarctic ocean*

when starting in Brisbane), showing that coupling landing probabilities with time stages increases the effect of the landscape.

Supplementary Figure 5. Results of simulation experiments. A. Simulated vs. inferred values of λ for a simulation without landscape. B. Inferred values of λ when inference is made with a non-stratified model vs. a stratified model in the same simulation of (A).

Supplementary Figure 6. Proportion of pixels per node recovered in each simulation when simulating with plate tectonics and a landscape and using the same paleogeographic model for the inference. Each bar represents a simulated tree, and the height of each bar is the proportion of nodes with at least 50% of the simulated pixels retrieved in the 95% of the cumulative density function of the ancestral pixel probabilities. The gray tones indicate the amount of recovered pixels, starting in light gray (50-60%) and ending in solid black (90-100%), in groups of 10%.

Supplementary Figure 7. The same trees were used for *supp. Fig. 6*, but using a model with current landscape and time stages each 5 Myr for the inference. See the caption of *supp. Fig. 6* for an explanation.

Supplementary Figure 8. The same trees were used for supp. Fig. 6, but using a model without landscape for the inference. See the caption of supp. Fig. 6 for an explanation.

Supplementary Figure 9. Phylogenetic relationships of Sapindaceae used in this work. On the left, the tree with the node numbers indicated; on the right, the same tree with the

branches colored by its average speed (in Km/Myr) log10 scaled, colored from purple (low probability) to red (high probability).

Supplementary Figure 10. Plot of the likelihood function for the Sapindaceae dataset. The left panel shows the likelihood function for the whole data. The right panel shows the likelihood function without the four faster branches.

Supplementary Figure 11. Distribution of Sapindaceae over time. The maps approximate the lineage richness by adding the CDF values for all lineages alive at the end of a given time stage and scaling to the maximum value in each time stage. Results are rotated to present geography.

Supplementary Figure 12. Ancestral pixel probabilities for the nodes assigned to the family, subfamily, and tribal ranks. Groups with a single terminal are not displayed. For the node IDs, see supplementary figure 9.